

SLIDING WEAR PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOFIBER AND NANOTUBE REINFORCED RUBBERS

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1 Introduction

Carbon nanofibers (CNF) and carbon nanotubes (CNT) are now commercially available and their application potential in rubbers of both thermoplastic and thermoset (crosslinked) types became under spot of vivid interest.

It was also early recognized that these novel one-dimensional (1D) reinforcements should be well dispersed and at the same time to have a good bonding toward the related matrix. Apart of improvements in the mechanical properties, further benefits, such as enhanced thermal, chemical and fire resistance, are expected from CNF and CNT in rubbers.

2 Experimental

Major goal of this work was to check whether the resistance to sliding wear can be improved by incorporation of CNF and multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) in rubbers.

As rubbers hydrogenated acrylonitrile butadiene rubber (HNBR) [1-2], and a polypropylene-based thermoplastic dynamic vulcanizate (TPV) [3] were preferentially used. HNBR blends with fluororubber (FKM) were also involved in this study [4]. The rubbers were modified with CNF and MWCNT via melt compounding. The tensile mechanical properties of the “nanoreinforced” rubbers were determined according to the related standards. The dispersion state of the nanofillers was studied by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Sliding wear tests were run on different tribotests, viz. pin(steel)-on-plate(rubber) /POP/, ring(steel)-on-plate(rubber) /ROP/ and oscillation wear or fretting (steel cylinder on rubber plate) configurations. The

test set-ups are summarized schematically in Figure 1.

Wear parameters, i.e. coefficient of friction and specific wear rate, of the CNF and MWCNT reinforced rubbers were determined and compared and compared with those of mixes containing no and or traditional fillers (carbon black, silica).

The wear development and mechanisms were studied by white light profilometry and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

3 Results

The sliding wear performance of the rubbers with CNF and MWCNT was usually better than the neat and traditionally filled (carbon black, silica) rubbers. However, the wear characteristics strongly depended on the set-up and testing conditions of the corresponding tribotests.

Figure 2 shows that the steady-state coefficient of friction (COF) highly depends on the test set-up and in lesser extent of the type and amount of the filler used. Note that the fillers were introduced in various parts per hundred rubber (phr) amounts.

In contrast to COF, the specific wear rate was more prominently reduced by MWCNT than by silica incorporation in the same amount – cf. Figure 3.

The sliding wear performance of HNBR mixes containing carbon black, silica and MWCNT in 20 phr was determined [2]. It was established that the lowest COF and highest resistance to sliding wear was achieved with carbon black and MWCNT fillers. The type of fillers affected the failure mode under sliding conditions markedly [1-2].

When HNBR/FKM (1/1) blends were reinforced by MWCNT, HNBR formed the continuous phase in

which the MWCNTs were preferentially embedded [4] – cf. Figure 4. This did not yield a further improvement in the tribological performance against the expectation.

Vapor-grown CNF was incorporated in TPV (Santoprene®) up to 5 phr from an aqueous dispersion using an ethylene/propylene/diene rubber (EPDM) as carrier (fixed at 5 phr) [4]. The tribological results were discouraging, neither the COF nor the specific wear rate were reduced in the expected range. This was traced to two effects: i) CNF was preferentially located in the PP and carrier EPDM, and ii) CNF possibly worked as absorbent for the processing oil, present in substantial amount in the TPV. As a consequence the initial morphology of the TPV has been changed. Such effects should be considered during the development of CNF- and MWCNT-containing recipes.

The effects of CNF and MWCNT on the sliding wear properties were summarized in book chapters recently [5-7]. The published tribological results, compared with those reported on rubber/clay systems [8-9] underline the straightforward use of CNF and (MW)CNT in rubbers foreseen for wear (abrasion, sliding) resistance products. However, the related research and development works are faced to big challenges outlined below.

4 Outlook and future trends

The tasks to be solved next are the followings:

- To achieve a better dispersion of CNF and CNT versions in rubber matrices
- To create a strong interphase with the rubber matrix
- To avoid, or just opposed, to trigger the selective enrichment in one of the phases of rubber blends

There are several straightforward strategies to meet the above tasks. To improve the dispersion of highly entangled CNFs and CNTs the latter should be predispersed in suitable masterbatches. The matrix material of the masterbatch is not necessarily a rubber. The author's presently favored concept is the predispersion of the above nanofillers in solid carrier materials which ensure further beneficial properties

in the rubber mixes, such as reduced melt viscosity. Masterbatches containing CNF, CNT may also contain traditional fillers, like carbon black and silica not only from economical reasons.

Functionalized, grafted CNFs and CNTs were rarely incorporated in rubbers by contrast to thermoplastic and thermoset resin systems. In this field considerable research and development work can be prophesized for the near future.

Rubbers are usually blended. It was shown in some of our works (e.g. [3-4] that CNF and CNT are usually embedded in one of the rubber components. In some cases this is not advantageous because homogeneous nanofiller distribution would yield the optimum properties. In other cases, such preferential dispersion would be highly beneficial to achieve given properties, for example electric conductivity in a rubber blend of interpenetrating network (IPN) structure. The necessary percolation here could be reached with substantially lower amount of these nanofillers compared to a rubber blend of the same structure the components of which show no preferential embedding of CNT or CNF in one of its constituents.

It is noteworthy that incorporation of CNF and (MW)CNT may be associated with other beneficial effects (e.g. resistance to fast decompression being a crucial issue in the sealing technology, or delayed degradation due to radical scavenging and absorption possibilities through these nanofillers). The clarification of these issues requires further work. Nonetheless, the feeling of the author is that the future work of rubber/CNF and rubber/CNT combinations will focus on “functional rubbers”, i.e. for such systems in which the reinforcing effect of these nanofillers is less important compared to other benefits.

References

- [1] D. Felhös, J. Karger-Kocsis and D. Xu: “Tribological testing of peroxide cured HNBR with different MWCNT and silica contents under dry sliding and rolling conditions against steel”, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 108, pp. 2840-2851, 2008
- [2] D. Xu, J. Karger-Kocsis and A. K. Schlarb: “Friction and wear of HNBR with different fillers under dry

sliding and rolling conditions” *eXPRESS Polym. Lett.*, 3, pp. 126-136, 2009

- [3] J. Karger-Kocsis, D. Felhös and R. Thomann: “Tribological behavior of a carbon-nanofiber-modified Santoprene thermoplastic elastomer under dry sliding and fretting conditions against steel”, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 108, pp. 724-730, 2008
- [4] D. Xu, J. Karger-Kocsis, Z. Major and R. Thomann: “Unlubricated rolling wear of HNBR/FKM/MWCNT compounds against steel”, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 112, pp. 1461-1470, 2009
- [5] J. Karger-Kocsis and D. Felhös: Friction and sliding wear of “nanomodified” rubbers and their coatings: Some new development in “*Tribology of Polymeric Nanocomposites*” (Eds.: K. Friedrich and A. K. Schlarb), Elsevier, Amsterdam, Chapter 13, pp. 304-324, 2008
- [6] K. G. Gatos and J. Karger-Kocsis: Rubber/clay nanocomposites: Preparation, properties and application in “*Rubber Nanocomposites: Preparation, Properties and Applications*” (Eds.: S. Thomas and R. Stephen), Wiley, Singapore, Chapter 7, pp. 169-195, 2010
- [7] D. Felhös and J. Karger-Kocsis: Friction and wear of rubber nanocomposites containing layered silicates and carbon nanotubes in “*Recent Advances in Elastomeric Nanocomposites*” (Eds.: V. Mittal, J. K. Kim and K. Pal), Springer, Berlin, Chapter 13, pp. 341-377, 2011
- [8] K. G. Gatos and J. Karger-Kocsis: Rubber-clay nanocomposites based on apolar diene rubbers in “*Rubber-Clay Nanocomposites: Science, Technology, and Applications*” (Ed.: M. Galimberti), Wiley, New York, Chapter 12, pp. 363-401, 2011
- [9] K. G. Gatos and J. Karger-Kocsis: Rubber-clay nanocomposites based on nitrile rubber in “*Rubber-Clay Nanocomposites: Science, Technology, and Applications*” (Ed.: M. Galimberti), Wiley, New York, Chapter 13, pp. 403-424, 2011

Fig.1. Set-up of the tribotests used to assess the sliding wear of rubber nanocomposites containing CNT and CNF

Fig.2. Measured average steady-state coefficient of friction (COF) values in the POP, ROP and fretting tests [1]. Note: phr means the amount of filler in part per hundred rubber unit.

Fig.3. Specific wear rate data in the POP, ROP and fretting tests [1]. For note cf. Figure 2.

Fig.4. Preferential distribution of MWCNT in the HNBR phase of peroxide cured HNBR/FKM (1/1) blend based on TEM inspection. Note that the F-distribution is mapped in the right hand-side TEM picture.